

Synthetic studies and structural aspects of some novel metallacyclic compounds incorporating nitrogen, oxygen and/or sulfur atoms[†]

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Recent development on new synthetic and structural aspects of some novel metallacyclic compounds incorporating nitrogen, oxygen and/or sulfur atoms pursued actively in our laboratories have been reviewed. Attention has been mainly focused on recent advancements on Al, In, Ga, Ge, Sn, Ti, Zr, As, Sb and Bi derivatives.

Introduction

Unprecedented spurt in the original literature on metal-oxygen/metal-nitrogen as well as metal-sulfur compounds of particularly main group elements, pursued actively in our laboratories also during the last decade, depicts the growing interest in the interaction of hard/soft donor ligands with class a/b type metals, as evinced by the publication of a large number of books¹⁻⁶, review articles⁷⁻¹⁶ and papers¹⁷⁻²².

The richness of metal (heterometal) alkoxides emerges from the accessibility of the soluble forms, oligomeric characteristic, interesting coordination chemistry, geometries and ease of hydrolysis; the last property has been increasingly used for the low temperature synthesis of oxide-ceramics by sol-gel/MOCVD processes²³⁻²⁸.

During the last couple of decades, the chemistry of metal (heterometal) alkoxides as synthones for the preparation of a wide variety of coordination compounds has been well documented^{5,6}. However, the application of metal-alkoxides for the preparation of ceramic materials by sol-gel/MOCVD processes is severely hampered because of the maintenance of the desired stoichiometry of the heterometallic species during the course of hydrolysis process or their formation into gaseous phase. Therefore, more recent research has drawn pointed attention on the synthesis and characterization of heteroleptic derivatives where labile alkoxy bridging ligands (in metal alkoxides) or halide ligands (in organometallic halides) are replaced by ligands which are more stable to hydrolysis or thermal treatment such as oxo^{29,30}, β -diketonate¹⁸, glycolate³¹⁻³³, Schiff base³⁴, oximes^{35,36} etc. Structural investigations of some of the new derivatives have also revealed many interesting facets.

In view of the above, the thrust of the present review

article is focused only on the synthetic and structural aspects of some novel metallacyclic compounds of related metal atoms (Al, Ga, In, Ge, Sn, Ti, Zr, As, Sb, Bi) including some organometallic species with mixed atom multidentate chelating ligands.

Al, Ga and In derivatives

As mentioned above, interest in the chemistry of alkoxides, β -diketonate and allied derivatives containing Al-O bond is growing continuously particularly due to their potential applications as precursors for ceramic materials by MOCVD/sol-gel techniques.

Amongst the metal alkoxides, the chemistry of aluminium isopropoxides received considerable attention. It had been reported to depict varying degree of molecular association, e.g. 2 to >4. This has been resolved to some extent by Mehrotra³⁷ in 1953 by the concept of *ageing phenomenon* in which initially dimeric vapour distills to a liquid trimeric species $[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3]_3$, which has been shown to recrystallize into a stable tetrameric form $[\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3]_4$. It is interesting to mention here that although, tris(acetylacetonato)aluminium(III), $\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3$ is monomeric with hexa-coordination around Al^{III} atom, yet, mixed alkoxo- β -diketonates of Al^{III} exhibit interesting structural variation^{38,39}.

More recently a novel heteroleptic species, bis(*N*-phenylsalicylideneiminato)aluminium-di- μ -isopropoxo-aluminium(III) has been prepared by the reaction of $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ and *N*-phenylsalicylideneimine in 1 : 1 molar ratio in refluxing anhydrous benzene³⁴,

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

The above dinuclear complex prefers unsymmetrical geometry containing 6- and 4-coordinated aluminium(III) atom as demonstrated by single crystal X-ray diffraction studies³⁴ (Fig. 1) rather than an expected symmetrical 5-coordinated structure $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}\{\text{CH}=\text{N}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)\}](\text{OPr}^i)\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}\{\text{CH}=\text{N}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)\}]$. Reactions of this complex with a variety of glycols have also been carried out in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 ratios. Similar types of reactions have also been carried out with the corresponding gallium and indium derivatives for the sake of comparison.

Fig. 1. Crystal and molecular structure of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}\{\text{CH}=\text{N}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)\}]_2 \mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_2$: (a) hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity, (b) all carbon and hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

In order to examine whether the stable basic unit (Fig. 1) can survive further nucleophilic attack, we carried out its reactions with simple as well as internally functionalized oximes. The binuclear products were generally obtained exhibiting different coordination states of the two aluminium(III) atoms. For the sake of comparative study molecular structure of a new pentacoordinated (2-acetylthiophenylloximate) bis(*N*-phenylsalicyldeneiminato) aluminium(III) was also carried out⁴⁰. Structure of this compound is unique and consists of a discrete monomeric unit with five-coordination around Al^{III} atom as shown in Fig. 2. Coordination environment around aluminium atom

Fig. 2. Crystal and molecular structure of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_5]_2\text{Al}[\text{ONC}(\text{Me})\text{C}_4\text{H}_3\text{S}]$.

can be described as a distorted trigonal bipyramidal. ²⁷Al NMR of this complex at room temperature exhibited a hump at δ 2.609 ppm indicating the presence of penta-coordination around Al^{III} atom.

In continuation to above, we also carried out the reactions of triethylaluminium with some Schiff bases⁴¹. Crystal and molecular structure of $[\text{Al}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}(\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_5)\}_2\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_5\}_2]^+\text{Br}^-$ was determined by X-ray

Fig. 3. Crystal and molecular structure of $[\text{Al}\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}(\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_5)\}_2\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_5\}_2]^+\text{Br}^-$

diffraction technique which shows an octahedral environment around aluminium(III) atom (Fig. 3).

Ge, Sn and Ti, Zr derivatives

Reactions of $\text{Ge}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ with a number of glycols in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios was carried out and the products were characterized by spectroscopic as well as structural technique. Structure of one of the compounds, $\text{Ge}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_2$ was determined by single crystal X-ray diffraction technique, which shows that it has a dimeric structure with Ge–O four-membered ring just like germanoxanes (Fig. 4)⁴².

Fig. 4. Crystal and molecular structure of $\text{Ge}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_2$.

Diorganotin(IV) complexes of the type $[\{R_2Sn(ONC(Me)C_5H_4N-2)\}_2O]_2$ ($R = Bu^n, Pr^n, Et, Me$)⁴³ was synthesized by the condensation reaction of R_2SnO with 2-NC₅H₄(Me)C=NOH in 1 : 1 molar ratio in refluxing anhydrous benzene/toluene and characterized by elemental analyses, IR and NMR (¹H, ¹³C and ¹¹⁹Sn) spectral studies. All these complexes displayed two Sn–CH resonances with different $^1J(^{119/117}Sn-^1H)$ and $^1J(^{119/117}Sn-^{13}C)$ coupling constants in the ¹H and ¹³C{¹H}NMR spectra, a characteristic property of dimeric tetraorganostannoxanes^{44,45}. In case of diethyl complex, the high field Sn–CH₂ resonances with the large value for $^1J(^{119/117}Sn-^{13}C)$ has been assigned to the exocyclic Et₂Sn group while, the low field Sn–CH₂ resonance with the smaller value of $^1J(^{119/117}Sn-^{13}C)$ to endocyclic Et₂Sn.

The ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra of all the above complexes display two well separated resonances as has been reported for tetraorganodistannoxanes, indicating dimeric structure in solution^{44–46}. The values of ¹¹⁹Sn chemical shift (–203.2 and –221.7 ppm) for the dipropyltin derivative indicate that the bonding should be similar to that of the dibutyltin derivative. However, the corresponding values of the ¹¹⁹Sn chemical shifts (–190.8 and –239.4 ppm) for the dimethyltin derivative suggest that the bonding should be similar to that of diethyltin complex.

The molecular structures of butyl $[\{Bu_2Sn(ONC(Me)C_5H_4N-2)\}_2O]_2$ (Fig. 5) and ethyl $[\{Et_2Sn(ONC(Me)C_5H_4N-2)\}_2O]_2$ (Fig. 6) derivatives have been established by single crystal X-ray diffraction studies. A comparison of the present results⁴³ with those reported earlier yields some interesting structural variations. The structure of butyl derivative is very similar to the previously reported for tetraorganodistannoxane structures^{44–46}.

However, the structure of ethyl derivative differs from the previously reported tetraorganodistannoxane structures.

Fig. 5. Crystal and molecular structure of $[\{Bu_2Sn(ONC(Me)C_5H_4N-2)\}_2O]_2$.

Fig. 6. Crystal and molecular structure of $[\{Et_2Sn(ONC(Me)C_5H_4N-2)\}_2O]_2$.

In contrast to $\{(R_2SnL)_2O\}_2$, where each tin is bonded to uninegative ligand L, in the case of $[\{Et_2Sn(ONC(Me)C_5H_4N-2)\}_2O]_2$ each of the exocyclic tin atom is bonded to two oximate anions and the oxime nitrogen of one of the anions is coordinated to endocyclic tin atom. Both endo- and exocyclic tin atoms in both the complexes are in distorted trigonal bipyramidal configuration with the R groups occupying the equatorial position. The asymmetric four-membered Sn₂O₂ ring is planar as usually observed. These molecules adopt a staircase conformation in the solid state.

The ORTEP plot of the corresponding methyl derivative $[\{Me_2Sn(ONC(Me)C_5H_4N-2)\}_2O]_2$ shows⁴⁷ that the basic structure is very similar to that of the corresponding ethyl derivative (Fig. 7), but with the addition of two free ligands that are hydrogen bonded to the ring nitrogen atom of oximate anion bonded to the exocyclic tin atom. This is the first structural investigation in which two free ligands are connected to the stannoxane framework in this manner. The two Sn–O distances of the four-membered planer Sn₂O₂ rings are identical (2.039 Å). The interesting feature of this structure is that the ring nitrogen of the same ligand moiety which was not taking part in coordination, is now

Fig. 7. Crystal and molecular structure of $[\{Me_2Sn(ONC(Me)C_5H_4N-2)\}_2O]_2$.

coordinating to the endocyclic tin atom⁴³. The geometry around each endocyclic tin atom is distorted octahedral with the methyl groups in *trans*-positions. The exocyclic tin atoms are in distorted trigonal bipyramidal environment with the methyl group in equatorial position.

In the structure of the free oxime, 2-NC₅H₄(Me)C=NOH (Fig. 8), hydrogen bonding involves the nitrogen atom of the ring to give O(1)–H(1)–N(2)' linkages that lead to chains⁴³.

Fig. 8. Crystal and molecular structure of 2-NC₅H₄(Me)C=NOH.

Reactions of *cis*-dialkoxybis(acetylacetonato)titanium(IV) [(*acac*)₂Ti(OPrⁱ)₂] with alkoxyalkanols in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios yield [(*acac*)₂Ti(OPrⁱ)_{2-n}(OCH₂CH₂OR')_n] (*n* = 1 or 2). On the basis of IR and NMR (¹H, ¹³C) spectral studies, a *cis*-octahedral environment around titanium has been proposed³⁰.

Single crystal X-ray structure of an oxo derivative, [(*acac*)₂TiO]₂ was also carried out (Fig. 9)³⁰.

Fig. 9. Crystal and molecular structure of [(*acac*)₂TiO]₂.

In continuation to above, corresponding Zr derivative, [(*acac*)₂Zr(OPrⁱ)₂] was also prepared and its reactions with internally functionalized oxime in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios were carried out. All these complexes were characterized by elemental analysis and spectral studies. To see the coordination pattern, crystal and molecular structure of one of the representative compounds⁴⁸, [(*acac*)₂Zr{ONC(Me)C₅H₄N-2}₂] was also carried out (Fig. 10). It is interesting to mention here that the ring nitrogen of the ligand moiety is coordinated to zirconium resulting in the formation of three-membered (Zr–O–N) ring. The overall coordination around Zr is eight.

Fig. 10. Crystal and molecular structure of [(*acac*)₂Zr{ONC(Me)C₅H₄N-2}₂].

As, Sb and Bi derivatives

Triorganoarsenic(V) oximates of the type [R₃As{ONC(Me)Ar}₂] (I) (R = Prⁱ, Buⁱ; Ar = C₅H₄N-2, C₄H₃O-2) was prepared⁴⁹ by the reaction of R₃AsCl₂ with the sodium salt of internally functionalized oximes in 1 : 2 molar ratio in anhydrous benzene. Redistribution reaction I with equimolar R₃AsX₂ yields the compounds of the type [R₃As(X){ONC(Me)Ar}] (X = Cl, Br, OH). All these compounds were characterized by elemental analyses, IR and NMR (¹H, ¹³C) spectroscopy.

Controlled hydrolysis of a representative monochloro complex [Pr₃As(Cl){ONC(Me)C₄H₃O-2}] yielded crystals of Pr₃As(OH)Cl. Single crystal X-ray diffraction study indicated that there is a distorted octahedral environment around arsenic atom. The ORTEP diagram of [Pr₃AsOH]⁺Cl⁻ (Fig. 11) clearly shows the hydrogen bonding between OH and the chloride ion. It also demonstrates, along with the bond lengths and bond angles that the distorted tetrahedral environment around arsenic that is found for [Ph₃AsOH]⁺^{50,51} regardless of the counter ion,

Fig. 11. Crystal and molecular structure of $[\text{Pr}_3\text{AsOH}]^+\text{Cl}^-$.

is also found in $[\text{Pr}_3\text{AsOH}]^+\text{Cl}^-$.

Using similar routes, reactions of triorganoantimony-dihalide with the internally functionalized oximes^{52,53} was also carried out. Crystal and molecular structures of $[\text{Me}_3\text{Sb}\{\text{ONC}(\text{Me})\text{C}_4\text{H}_3\text{O}-2\}_2]$ (Fig. 12a), $[\text{Me}_3\text{Sb}\{\text{ONC}(\text{Me})\text{C}_4\text{H}_3\text{S}-2\}_2]$ (Fig. 12b) and $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb}\{\text{ONC}(\text{Me})\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}-2\}_2]$ (Fig. 13) have been determined. The geometry around

Fig. 12. Crystal and molecular structure of (a) $[\text{Me}_3\text{Sb}\{\text{ONC}(\text{Me})\text{C}_4\text{H}_3\text{O}-2\}_2]$, (b) $[\text{Me}_3\text{Sb}\{\text{ONC}(\text{Me})\text{C}_4\text{H}_3\text{S}-2\}_2]$.

Fig. 13. Crystal and molecular structure of $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb}\{\text{ONC}(\text{Me})\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}-2\}_2]$.

the antimony atom in these compounds may be described as distorted trigonal bipyramidal with the carbon atom of SbR_3 unit in equatorial positions and two oxygen atoms of the oxime groups occupying axial positions.

In the structure of free oxime $2\text{-SC}_4\text{H}_3\text{C}(\text{Me})=\text{NOH}$ hydrogen bonding results in a dimer⁵², as depicted in Fig. 14, in contrast to the polymeric chain structure of $2\text{-NC}_5\text{H}_4\text{C}(\text{Me})=\text{NOH}$ (Fig. 8),

Fig. 14. Crystal and molecular structure of $2\text{-SC}_4\text{H}_3\text{C}(\text{Me})=\text{NOH}$.

whereas, $2\text{-OC}_4\text{H}_3\text{C}(\text{Me})=\text{NOH}$ is monomer with no hydrogen bonding (Fig. 15)⁵².

Fig. 15. Crystal and molecular structure of $2\text{-OC}_4\text{H}_3\text{C}(\text{Me})=\text{NOH}$.

Reactions of sodium/potassium salts of xanthates, dithiocarbamates and dialkyldithiophosphates with methylbismuth dichloride were carried out in 1 : 2 stoichiometric ratio in anhydrous benzene and products of the type $[\text{MeBi}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})_2]$ ($\text{R} = \text{Me}, \text{Et}, \text{Pr}^i$), $[\text{MeBi}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_2]$ ($\text{R} = \text{Me}, \text{Et}, 1/2\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{N}$) and $[\text{MeBi}\{\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OR})_2\}_2]$ ($\text{R} = \text{Me}, \text{Et}, \text{Pr}^i$) were isolated⁵⁴. All of these complexes were characterized by elemental analyses as well as by IR and NMR (^1H , ^{13}C and ^{31}P) spectral studies.

^{13}C CPMAS spectra of a few representative complexes have been recorded. The Bi–Me resonance in complexes $[\text{MeBi}(\text{S}_2\text{COMe})_2]$ and $[\text{MeBi}(\text{S}_2\text{CNMe}_2)_2]$ appear as an unresolved broad hump, however, in $[\text{MeBi}(\text{S}_2\text{CNEt}_2)_2]$

only one signal at $\delta 40.5$ appeared. Two sets of resonances were observed for the carbon atoms of the ligands, the CS_2 and ER (ER = OMe, NMe_2 , NEt_2) signals both being observed.

The X-ray structure of $[MeBi(S_2COMe)_2]$ (Fig. 16) indicates that the immediate environment around the central bismuth atom is distorted square-pyramidal. However, inclusion of a significant Bi-S intermolecular bond results in pentagonal pyramidal geometry.

Fig. 16. Crystal and molecular structure of $[MeBi(S_2COMe)_2]$.

Thermolysis of $[MeBi(S_2COPr^1)_2]$ in xylene indicated that it is a good precursor for pure Bi_2S_3 at low temperature.

Conclusion

Synthetic and structural aspects of heteroleptic derivatives provide a great insight as compared to the homoleptic derivatives. The above studies do indicate a variety of coordination geometries around the central metal atom, yet more efforts are required to understand their stabilities and applications.

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